

SOP Urea analysis during MR19-04

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1. Introduction

Urea is a small nitrogen containing organic molecule, for which recent studies have shown plays an important role in the marine nitrogen cycle, as it is rapidly turned over in the environment and acts as a nitrogen shuttle within the microbial loop. Urea is mostly produced in the ocean via excretion from heterotrophic organisms of all size classes from bacteria upwards, this urea provides a source of bioavailable nitrogen for heterotrophic bacteria, cyanobacteria and eukaryotic phytoplankton. There are only a few published reports for Urea in near surface waters from the oligotrophic Indian Ocean [Baer *et al.*, 2019] and Indian sector of the Southern Ocean [Thomalla *et al.*, 2011] with concentrations ranging from below detection (less than 10 nM) in the oligotrophic tropics up to 2.5 μM in the region between the subtropical front and the subantarctic front.

1.1. Reaction of Urea with oximes

The diacetyl monoxime colorimetric assay for urea was first developed for the detection of citrulline [Archibald, 1944; Fearon, 1939] and later for urea [Archibald *et al.*, 1945]. Other oximes also react with urea to form a coloured product, most notably dimethylglyoxime and nioxime [Butler *et al.*, 1981a; Liang *et al.*, 2019; Ohkuma, 1955; Siest, 1963; 1967; Siest *et al.*, 1968].

The method was first applied to determining the urea content of seawater by Newell *et al.* [1967] and has undergone a number of iterations since then. Firstly with the use of thiosemicarbazide (TSC) as a stabilizing agent [Aminot and Kerouel, 1982], then optimization of the reaction conditions and heating step [Mulvenna and Savidge, 1992]. A room temperature procedure was also developed [Goeyens *et al.*, 1998] as well as incorporating the use of liquid wave capillary cells (LWCC) to increase the sensitivity and lower detection limits [Chen *et al.*, 2015]. More recently a single reagent addition method was applied using the COLDER reagent [Alam *et al.*, 2017], originally developed for citrulline analysis [Knipp and Vařák, 2000].

For many years the exact chromophore produced in this reaction puzzled chemists, but work by Butler and colleagues [Butler and Hussain, 1981; Butler *et al.*, 1981b] have provided a plausible chemical species and mechanism, though this it is still often referred to in the literature as being unknown.

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- a R = Me
- b R = H

VIIIb is a carbonium species and this is the coloured product seen in the Urea-DAMO assay *Butler et al.* [1981b].

1.2. Potential Interferences

This reaction is not specific for urea as any ureido species can react with DAMO to form a coloured complex [*Butler and Hussain, 1981; Butler et al., 1981b*]. This includes Citrulline, Allantoin, Alloxan, Hydantoin and Xanthine [*Reay et al., 2019; Satoh and Katoh, 1989*]. It is possible that some of these compounds decompose to urea during the assay instead of reacting directly with DAMO as HPLC studies have shown the same peak as for urea [*Satoh and Katoh, 1989*]. Although there is no evidence to date of a significant bias in seawater samples arising from Citrulline having been observed [*Aminot and Kerouel, 1982; Price and Harrison, 1987*]. The interference caused by allantoin and thiourea is also thought to be negligible, as they are not found at sufficiently high concentrations in natural waters to cause serious problems [*Remsen, 1971*]. Uric acid may potentially interfere where there are high concentrations of aquatic birds [*Satoh and Katoh, 1989*].

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Table 1.1 Comparison of components of DAMO based methods for Urea:

Reference	DAMO (mg L ⁻¹)	TSC (mg L ⁻¹)	SCHC (mg L ⁻¹)	H ₂ SO ₄ (v/v)	Fe ³⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	Temperature (°C)	Reaction time	ε mol ⁻¹ L cm ⁻¹
[Newell et al., 1967]	710		8.57	11%		70	90 min	18,000
[Koroleff, 1983]	770		8.57	12.0%		75	120 min	11,000
[Mulvenna and Savidge, 1992]	1796	20.1		9.37%	0.85	85	20 min	16,000
[Goeyens et al., 1998]	1800	20.1		9.37%	0.85	R.T. 85	3 days 20 min	21,000 19,000
[Revilla et al., 2005]	1800	20.0		9.37%	0.85	R.T.	3 days	19,000
[Chen et al., 2015] - research	1500	10.0		20%	0.84	85	30 min	29,700
[Chen et al., 2015] - trace	1000	3.0		20%	0.84	85	30 min	24,000
[Alam et al., 2017]	1796	20.1		9.85%	0.51	R.T. 70	3 days 60 min	18,100 20,200
This work - COLDER	1788	19.9		9.82%	0.82	70	60 min	
This work – COLDER trace	1016	9.3		11.16%	0.93	70	60 min	

Notes: SCHC is semicarbazide hydrochloride. R.T. denotes Room Temperature.

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2. Sampling for Urea

We have 2 sets of sample bottles (125 mL Brown HDPE – set 1 is orange, set 2 is light blue) for collecting seawater. At least an hour prior to the deployment of the CTD station you are sampling, you will need to place one of these sets in our blue/grey bottle holder in the sampling space near the CTD with the station number marked on the box handle. This is so the sampling team can place the marked bottles into the appropriate hamper prior to the station commencing.

Seawater is collected as cleanly as possible from the Niskin-X's on the 36 bottle rosette using the 125 mL Brown HDPE bottles. It is best if the samples are collected via a tube with a gentle flow rate and that the bottle is rinsed 3 times before final collection of the sample. For MR19-04 we are sampling the upper 1600 m of the water column which represents Niskin bottles 36 to 20 and bottle 2 which is the chlorophyll maxima on most casts.

The seawater should then be filtered in the laboratory using the 0.2 µm syringe filtration (Sarstedt) system as soon as possible. For Leg 2, a 10 mL Teflon syringe and a 20 mL Plastic syringe were employed with comparable results. The 20 mL syringe is preferred as you can filter more water faster. Typically, there is little particulate matter in the water, so a new filter can be used every 6 samples, if you encounter a bloom then you can increase the number of filters used accordingly.

The first 10 mL through a new filter was discarded immediately as this contains anti-microbial compounds from the filter itself. The sample bottles for the filtered water were rinsed with 2 aliquots of 10 mL of filtrate before collecting either 20 (30 mL LDPE – green labels) or 40 mL (60 mL LDPE – white labels) of sample.

If it is not possible to analyze the samples immediately, the samples should be kept in the 4°C room before returning to the laboratory for analysis within 24 hours.

Notes:

In refilling the syringe it is best practice to disconnect the Luer lock with the filter, withdraw the piston, reconnect the filter via the luer lock, fill the cylinder barrel of the syringe with sample and then reinsert the piston.

Take care not to remove the syringe piston while the Luer lock is connected to a filter as this will ultimately distort the cylinder barrel of the syringe.

3. Materials

3.1. Sampling Equipment

Bottles (numbered) for sampling from CTD Niskin (Brown HDPE – 125 mL)

Teflon Syringe (10 mL Savillex) or PP Syringe (10 or 20 mL)

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25 mm 0.2 µm Syringe filters (Sarstedt)

Sample bottles (numbered) for filtered seawater (LDPE - 30 mL)

3.2. Chemicals and Equipment for Reagent Preparation

0.60 g Urea

0.19 g Thiosemicarbazide (TSC)

0.15 g FeCl₃

3.40 g Diacetylmonoxime (DAMO)

Ultrapure water

3.3. Equipment for Analysis

Fisher dry bath (powered onboard via transformer 100 to 230 V)

Ocean Optics spectrophotometer (Maya or Flame)

Ocean Optics lightsource (DH-mini)

Fibre Optics (400 µm SR)

LWCC-3050

4. Preparation of Reagents

4.1. Preparation of COLDER Reagent

DAMO: Monoxime solution was prepared by dissolving 3.4 g of diacetyl monoxime (CH₃-CO-CNOH-CH₃; Supelco) in 100 mL of MQ water.

TSC: Thiosemicarbazide solution was prepared by dissolving 0.19 g of the pre-weighed thiosemicarbazide (NH₂-CS-NH-NH₂; Sigma) in 20 mL of MQ water. It apparently has not been noted in earlier works but TSC is only sparingly soluble in water: 10 mg/mL at 20°C (Santa Cruz Biotechnology). During Leg 2 the TSC was initially in the fridge but it kept precipitating out, so it was kept in the lab.

Iron solution: 0.15 g of Ferric Chloride (FeCl₃; Sigma) is dissolved in 10 mL of MQ water.

Diluted Sulfuric Acid Solution: 240 mL of 95% concentrated Sulfuric acid is slowly added to 188 mL of MQ in a 500 mL Teflon Bottle in the fumehood next to the laboratory. EXTREME CAUTION required: The reaction of concentrated sulfuric acid with water is an extremely exothermic reaction and the bottle will heat up very quickly, it is best to slowly add the acid to the MQ over the course of an hour or so, to reduce the risk of boiling or spitting of acid. Note that the heat generated will melt LDPE bottles so never use them with concentrated or slightly diluted sulfuric acid solutions. A lab coat, gloves and safety glasses are required for this procedure.

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Reagent A

Reagent A was prepared by mixing 3.66 mL of the DAMO solution with 146 μ L of the TSC solution (25:1 mix) in a 30 ml LDPE bottle.

Reagent B

Reagent B was prepared by adding with 90 μ L of the Ferric chloride solution to 100 mL of the diluted sulfuric acid in a Teflon Bottle (125 mL capacity).

COLDER Reagent (for 30 samples)

The COLDER was prepared by adding 12.2 mL of reagent B directly into the Reagent A bottle. The COLDER reagent was used immediately (see below).

4.2. Preparation of COLDER reagent for low levels of UREA

For Trace-level seawater (< 200 nM) samples the preparation of the COLDER reagent is altered as follows:

Reagent A

Reagent A was prepared by mixing 1.83 mL of the DAMO solution with 60 μ L of the TSC solution (25:1 mix) in a 30 ml LDPE bottle.

Reagent B

Reagent B was prepared as indicated above.

COLDER Reagent (for 30 samples)

The COLDER was prepared by adding 12.2 mL of reagent B directly into the Reagent A bottle. The COLDER reagent was used immediately (see below).

4.3. Preparation of Working Standards

UREA: A standard solution of urea ($\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2$; Sigma) is prepared by dissolving 0.6 g of the pre-weighed Urea to 100 mL of MQ. This results in an 0.1 M primary solution. This solution is stored at 4 °C in an LDPE bottle; it can remain stable for more than 1 year.

Working standard (0-1 μ M): A working standard solution (20 μ M) is created by adding 20 μ L of the primary standard to 100 mL of MQ.

Working standard low level (0-200 nM): A secondary standard (400 μ M) is produced by the addition of 80 μ L of the primary standard to 20 mL of MQ. A working standard (3.985 μ M) is then created by the addition of 200 μ L of the secondary standard to 20 mL of MQ.

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Standard preparation scheme I –Urea Working Standard

Std#	MQ(uL)	Work (uL)	Reagent(uL)	[Urea] nM
1	1540	0	460	0.0
2	1520	20	460	200.0
3	1500	40	460	400.1
4	1480	60	460	600.1
5	1460	80	460	800.1
6	1440	100	460	1000.1

Standard preparation scheme II – Urea Working Standard low level

Std#	MQ(uL)	Work (uL)	Reagent(uL)	[Urea] nM
1	1540	0	460	0.0
2	1520	20	460	39.8
3	1500	40	460	79.7
4	1480	60	460	119.5
5	1460	80	460	159.4
6	1440	100	460	199.2

Note: normally the procedure has been to add 770 μ L of MQ to each of the 6 vials and then add 770, 750, 730, 710, 690 and 670 μ L to the standard vials respectively. The working standard is then added and finally the COLDER reagent when prepared.

5. Analysis Protocol

- (i) Dry bath heating
 - 1) Prior to starting, label the Eppendorf vials according to the station number and niskin (e.g. 68-02 is Station 68, Niskin 2) and arrange them in one of black box vial holders.
 - 2) Plug in the transformer for the dry bath and then turn on the dry bath (switch is at the back of the device).
 - 3) Using gloves and preferably a lab coat, carefully add 1540 μ L (2 x 770 μ L additions) of the filtered seawater to a clean, dry 2 mL Eppendorf vial. Take care not to contaminate the samples by contacting any surfaces or articles of clothing that may have sweat on them etc.
 - 4) Add the COLDER reagent to the Eppendorf vial and securely close the top.
 - 5) Place the vials in the dry bath heater block.

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- 6) Once all the vials are in place, start the dry bath heating by pushing the start button. The dry bath is already set to ramp up to 70° C and then hold that temperature for an hour. You can check the progress of the dry bath once it is running by pushing the switch button (alternates between current temperature and time since it reached the required temperature).
- 7) At the end of the one hour heating period a short audible alarm will ring and the heating will turn off on the dry bath. At this stage the samples should be carefully removed from the heating block and placed into a black vial holder, once filled with samples the lid should be shut to keep it light tight.
- 8) Allow 30-40 minutes for the samples to cool to close to room temperature. If required samples could be cooled quicker by placing in ice or in the 4°C room, though for Leg 2 cooling in the laboratory was normally sufficient.
- 9) During the cooling period, if you are not already running other samples, you should set up the Ocean Optics Maya2000Pro Spectrophotometer connected via 400 µm optical fibres to the LWCC-3050 and DH-mini light source. Keep the shutter on the DH-mini closed if changing the optical fibres to avoid looking at the light source directly. Normal operating conditions for this set up are as follows:

Deuterium lamp: on

Halogen lamp: off (the Halogen lamp adds too much IR)

Integration time: 12 ms

Scans to average: 20

- 10) Obtain a light spectrum for absorbance measurements after having run several holdup volumes of MQ water through the LWCC-3050. Close the shutter on the DH-mini and take a dark spectrum. Open the shutter again, switch to absorbance mode on Spectrasuite and flush more MQ through and check that the spectrum remains stable on or near zero.
- 11) Pull the samples through the LWCC-3050 using a syringe and measure the absorbance spectrum of each sample. Save each sample spectrum into that day's urea directory (e.g. c:/MR19-04Leg3/Shipboard data/200101/Urea) using the following naming convention:

Standards

YYMMDDMR19-04SxxxStd0n

Where YY is Year, MM is month, DD is day, MR19-04 is the expedition identifier, Sxxx is the station number and Std0n is the nth standard.

Samples

YYMMDDMR19-04SxxxNzzDyyyy

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Where YY is Year, MM is month, DD is day, MR19-04 is the expedition identifier, Sxxx is the station number, Nzz is the Niskin number and Dyyyy is the depth of the sample.

e.g. 200101MR19-04S001N02D0100 would be for a sample from the 1st of January 2020, Station 1, Niskin 2 at a depth of 100m. For sample from the chlorophyll maximum (Niskin 2), you can find the depth at which the bottle was fired from the bottle file available on the internet Z:/ctd/proc/xxxM001 where xxx is the station number.

12) The high sulfuric acid content of the samples makes them less prone to bubbles so you can put one sample through after another. Alternatively, as for the LWCC-4100, you can pull water through, measure the sample and then alternatively slowly and carefully push air back through, collecting the solution in the brown waste container prior to loading in the next sample. This normally results in the next sample coming back to the same baseline at 700 nm. The waste sample in the syringe can be put down the sink, just remember as it has a high sulfuric acid content you should carefully flush/dilute it with tapwater when clearing up afterwards.

13) Once all the standards and samples are completed, flush the LWCC-3050 system with MQ until the signal returns to baseline and then gently push air through the system so that it is dry.

(ii) Room temperature analysis

An alternative approach [Goeyens *et al.*, 1998] to using the 70° C dry bath is to store the samples and standards after the addition of the COLDER reagent at the ambient laboratory temperature 22 °C in the dark and then measure their absorbances 3 days later using the same procedure as outlined above.

6. Data processing

6.1. Convert to text file

In order to read the file in Matlab or excel we need to convert the original Spectrasuite Prospec datafiles into text files (with header information) using the convert spectrum window in Spectrasuite. Unfortunately, this is a somewhat laborious approach as you need to identify the source directory (e.g. c:/MR19-04Leg3/Shipboard data/200101/Urea) and then repeat the process to make it also the destination directory.

It is very important to save the data as text files with headers into the same directory as the original ProcSpec files. If you save them as ProcSpec files (the default in SpectraSuite) it will overwrite the first file and you will lose that data.

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6.2. Run Matlab script to process standards and samples

A Matlab script is provided for this expedition that will batch load the converted spectrasuite text files found in the current directory by running the command:

```
[1,ndataStd,Std,a525Std] = MR1904loadUreaStd()
```

This will then open a window where you can select all the files corresponding to standards. You can then plot the standard curve and save the data (in this example it was for station 66 of Leg2:

```
plot(Std,a525Std,'*r')
```

```
save 191221MR19-04S066UreaStd
```

The sample data can be loaded similarly:

```
[1,ndata,a525,Stn,Depth,Niskin] = MR1904loadUrea()
```

To plot this data as a function of depth and then save it using the following commands:

```
plot(a525,-Depth,'*r')  
save 191221MR19-04S066Urea
```

Finally, to export the data to Excel, use the following command and then cut and paste the data from the screen.

```
x=[Niskin',a525']
```

6.3. Paste into Excel sheet and add to ODV Bottle file

To paste data from Matlab (i.e. standard or sample absorbances) into an excel file use the data Wizard function under paste in Excel and enter it into the spreadsheet. The excel spreadsheet is set up to automatically calculate the sensitivity and intercept for the standards and then use these values to calculate the sample concentrations.

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